

accting

AdvanCing behavioural
Change Through
an INclusive Green deal

Operational Guidelines and Recommendations -1st Cycle

European Citizen Science Association (ECSA)

N. Sharma (ECSA), N. Zaharis (SEERC), A. Denis (YW), S. Strid (UGOT), A. Gül Altınay (SU) F. Gajdusek (ZSI), C. Zorell (ORU), C. Green (ORU), G. Szüdi (ZSI), A. Kerremans (YW), G. Quinti (K&I), M. Klados (SEERC), G. Pellegrini Masini (NTNU), A. Vivas (SEERC), M. Cacace (K&I), B. Borhan Türeli (SU), E. Düzel (SU)

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List of Acronyms

BIPOC	Black, Indigenous and People of Colour
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CC	Climate Change
CSO	Civil Society Organization
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
DRD	Disaster risk deduction
EA	Energy Audit
EEM	Energy Efficiency Measures
ESG	Environment, Social, Governance
EU	European Union
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
GD	Green Deal
HR	Human Resources
ILC	Indigenous and local communities
ILK	Indigenous and local knowledge
IPBES	Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services
IUCN	International Union for Conservation of Nature
NGO	Non-Government Organization
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SMEs	Small and Medium Enterprises
UNDRR	United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction
WP	Work Package
WWF	World Wildlife Fund

The ACCTING project

The European Green Deal foresees efficient use of resources for a circular and clean economy. However, inequalities emerge in the context of its policy and interventions. The EU-funded ACCTING project mobilises research experimentation and innovation to promote an inclusive and socially just European Green Deal focusing on the inequalities produced by its policies. The project explores the impact of Green Deal policy initiatives on individual and collective behaviours, provides evidence, and empowers policymakers and stakeholders to anticipate policy responses and potential negative influences, and to mitigate such impacts in decision-making. ACCTING collects new data on Green Deal policy interventions and co-designs and implements pilot actions to reduce or prevent policy-related inequalities.

Project Consortium

	European Science Foundation (ESF)
	Örebro University (ORU)
	Yellow Window (YW)
	Knowledge and Innovation (K&I)
	Zentrum für Soziale Innovation (ZSI)
	Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU)
	ICLEI - Local Governments for Sustainability, European Secretariat
	Sabanci University (SU)
	Instituto de Geografia e Ordenamento de Território (IGOT)
	Southeast European Research Center (SEERC)
	Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iasi (UAIC)
	European Citizen Science Association (ECSA)
	University of Gothenburg (UGOT)

Summary

This deliverable is an anthology of policy recommendations developed in the form of factsheets for three target groups: policy makers, civil society organizations and businesses/employers (private /public). It stems from the results of the first research cycle of ACCTING. The development process of the policy recommendations is discussed in detail here.

Introduction

This is the first deliverable for WP5 drafted at the end of the first research cycle of ACCTING. The first activity planned for WP5 was a workshop within the ACCTING consortium that took place on May 4, 2023, in Lisbon. Insights from WP2, WP3 and WP4 were used as a starting point for the workshop. The inputs from the workshop participants helped to generate concrete topics that these recommendations are directed towards. This deliverable presents operational recommendations developed in the form of factsheets for the target groups such as policymakers, civil society organizations and businesses/employers. Two sets of factsheets are developed for each target group focused on six topics: accessibility to healthy and environmentally friendly food for the marginalized and vulnerable group, valuing local and indigenous knowledge for disaster management, inclusive civil societies for an inclusive Green Deal, gender+ inclusive agricultural policies and civil societies for and with small farmers, inspiring corporate social responsibilities for an inclusive Green Deal and business–employees alliance for behavioural change. Some factsheets in the deliverable have provided recommendations to actors beyond their target group as some topics addressed here need attention of multiple target groups simultaneously.

The factsheets consist of a brief overview of the inequalities, findings from ACCTING that reflect those inequalities, set of operational recommendations, better stories that refer to promising practices that are working to attenuate these inequalities and concludes with the Green Deal policy areas that the factsheets are directly linked to.

As a part of the communication and dissemination strategy these factsheets are aimed at informing the policy makers at local, regional level and transnational level, civil society organizations working for vulnerable and marginalized groups and employers in both public and private sector on improving Green Deal policies such that present inequalities can be diminished and further increase in inequalities can be impeded. ACCTING research so far has highlighted the need to complement Green Deal with policy actions at European and national level that specifically address vulnerabilities and prevent inequalities. This document on policy recommendations is therefore expected to have a valuable contribution to this.

Methodology

The policy recommendations are developed following the inputs from the research insights of:

- WP2 mapped bottom-up initiatives in 27 member states, the UK, Turkey, Serbia, Norway, Japan, US and Brazil.

- WP3 implemented experimental studies along 8 thematic research lines resulting among other insight into 410 narratives and
- WP4 developed and executed the open studios: a hands-on series of workshops with consortium members and inputs from advisory board members and external experts.

Results from the first cycle of experimental studies were considered to generate themes that were further elaborated to formulate the recommendations. These themes were extracted from the insights and site-specific analysis of the 13 countries involved in the WP3 research activity. After that, action ideas generated from the Open Studios were considered and further developed into recommendations. These action ideas were within the eight research lines¹ of ACCTING and were directed towards various target groups such as policy makers, businesses and civil society organizations.

Eventually, a hands-on workshop carried out with the consortium partners helped in further funnelling down the elaborate themes of WP3 and action ideas from WP4 into a concrete topic to be developed into recommendations for the above-mentioned target groups. The recommendations were developed as six factsheets by the consortium partners. These factsheets further received feedback from the advisory board members and external topic specific experts. Finally, these feedbacks were incorporated into the respective factsheets and a final version was prepared.

Operational recommendations

The operational recommendations consist of different factsheets with recommendations for policy makers, civil society organizations and businesses/employers (public and private) aimed towards reshaping policies. Each factsheet addresses specific target group; however, some topics need attention from a set of actors. Considering this some of the factsheets, namely factsheets for civil society organizations have tried to address the policymakers as well.

¹ <https://accting.eu/research-lines/>

Recommendations to Policymakers

Promoting access to healthy and environmentally friendly food for the marginalised and vulnerable

Contributors: Nikita Sharma (ECSA), Carolin Zorell (ORU)

Access to environmentally sustainable food, urban mobility and urban green spaces – prerequisites for a successful Green Deal

Access to healthy and environmentally friendly food is limited, especially for those living in marginalised urban (and rural) areas. It often requires much time to find and access food that is locally produced, seasonal, and organic, and when available it tends to be expensive. The current geopolitical situation exacerbates the problem, having led to dramatic increases in food prices all over the EU. Particularly, people with low-income and/or who are marginalised in multiple ways struggle to afford food, especially food that is fresh and healthy. Therefore, it is crucial that local and regional governments adapt their policy measures and make access to locally produced, seasonal healthy food a priority, especially in marginalised neighbourhoods. In doing so, policies concerning the production and provision of local food, urban mobility and urban green spaces are of major concern.

Findings from ACCTING

Based on 410 narratives related to food and transport, the ACCTING consortium concludes that **access to environmentally friendly food is largely connected with urban food systems and mobility issues**: it often requires much time to find and access food that is local, seasonal, organic, and affordable.

Intriguing and innovative observations are²:

- **The lack of proximity to stores, or lack of knowledge where to find and access stores** that sell environmentally friendly food, is a major hindering factor to changing eating habits.
- **A lack of public transport** in areas where vulnerable people live – even in some areas of big cities – and **lack of access to supermarkets**.
- **Eating seasonal/locally produced food is more time-consuming** because there are fewer stores offering these products, they are more difficult to find/identify; and many of them have a poorly diversified product range requiring customers to go to several stores.
- **Lack of family support, community networks, and access to land or farmer (markets)** are fundamental barriers to behaviour change.

Informants emphasised the **importance of street markets and small market stores** providing them not only cheaper, but also fresher, seasonal, and local produces. In other regions, the use of **urban gardens to cultivate food** was found to be a common practice linked to economic needs and concern for sustainable food consumption.

² Zorell, C., & Strid, S. (eds.) (2023). D3.2 ACCTING Report on first cycle experimental studies. Confidential report delivered to the European Commission 28 April 2023. 281 pages.

Recommendations

1. Make it obligatory for supermarkets to create a supply of local, seasonal, and organic products.

To foster environmentally friendly food consumption in a socially just way, it is crucial to reshape food systems and emphasise the broader and universal provision of seasonal, organic, and locally produced food. A key policy measure to promote such a shift implies the establishment of quotas for supermarkets to offer these products. This can also alleviate accessibility problems related to transport and time poverty.

2. Include schemes to support community-led local initiatives.

Community-led local initiatives and food cooperatives can crucially help facilitating shorter supply chains and broader access to food, and thereby help making small-scale agriculture more viable and strengthening regional food producers and networks. Policymakers can initiate foster programmes to support and promote such initiatives. This should be complemented by sustained financial incentives for urban farming, and for farmers to transition to organic farming.

3. Facilitate access to information where people can find nutritious, environmentally sustainable, and affordable food in their neighbourhoods.

The establishment of online platforms or databases that collect information about selling points can help establish a more efficient system to inform people where to find local, seasonal, and organic food. This should be accompanied by campaigns that raise awareness about local (farmers') markets and direct-to-consumer food distribution

initiatives; particularly targeting those in marginalised neighbourhoods to ensure the platforms and knowledge reach them.

4. Establish urban gardens in low-income areas.

Lack of access to food can be reduced by giving vulnerable groups immediate access to gardening spaces. The creation of urban gardens should also be accompanied by financially supported, educational programs that teach individuals how to cultivate their own healthy food, fostering a culture of self-sufficiency and sustainability within communities.

5. Promote farmers markets in marginalised areas and make space for the sale of local produce.

Public authorities should explicitly prioritise the allocation of space to farmers, small-scale food producers and other people for selling local and regional, ecological food products. Policymakers can also set incentives to establish more local farmers markets in marginalised areas. This includes streamlining regulatory processes and reducing bureaucratic hurdles.

6. Extend the concept of the 15-minute city to peri-urban areas.

With growing urbanisation and traffic, the concept of the “15-minute city” has attracted much attention, based on the idea that everyone should have access to basic daily needs within a short walk or bike ride. The reach of the “15-minute city” should be expanded to include peri-urban areas, where it would benefit many families, seniors, and other vulnerable groups of people with restricted mobility.

7. Prioritise local and seasonal food in public procurement.

Public actors are role models, and they spend large sums on procurement of food and other products. They need to use this leverage and prioritise the purchase of regional/local and seasonal food products, both to provide for positive examples to the population, and to support the development and establishment of local food producers that sell seasonal and organic produces.

8. Price in environmental impacts.

Current prices are not reflecting the environmental costs of food. In addition, environmental certification schemes tend to be costly to obtain, altogether making it for small-scale organic producers hard to compete. There is an urgent need for policymakers introduce a price scheme reflecting environmental costs of food properly, for instance through a tax related to food miles, water consumption, and/or pesticides use. Policymakers should also initiate a transformation of the certification processes towards prices adjusted to the size of the farm and amount of produce.

Better stories - some inspirational cases

In ACCTING, we look for inspiring bottom-up initiatives as *Better Stories*, a concept borrowed from Dina Georgis³ to refer promising practices that can instil ideas for how to advance individual and collective behavioural change as envisioned by the Green Deal.

FINLAND

Tuusula, Finland

One such better story comes from Finland, where the ***Oma Maa (Our Land) Cooperative***⁴ has made city-based citizens become farm co-owners. The members help with certain farming tasks, while also having access to the locally produced food through food pick-up points in the city. This initiative has helped community members lead more environmental-friendly lifestyles and try to be self-sustaining by growing food locally and taking care of each other. The initiative also contributes to strengthening the link between urban and rural settings.

BULGARIA

Sofia, Bulgaria

A similar inspiring story comes from Bulgaria, where the members of the cooperative ***Hrankoop***⁵ collaborate with local organic food producers. The cooperative's key activities include having the members work in local organic farms, organising weekly farmers markets, developing educational programs, and the promotion of urban agriculture.

PORTUGAL

Faro, Portugal

The Solidarity Kitchen Garden ***Horta Urbana Solidária de Faro***⁶ is an urban vegetable garden with 100 m² production area, distributed on the rooftop terrace of the municipal market of Faro. It cultivates vegetables, aromatic, medicinal, and spice plants, following the principles of organic/traditional farming. The main aim of this initiative is to diminish the urban/rural gap (short food supply chain) by promoting organic production in an urban context, to empower and promote the social inclusion of disabled children and low-income families and to promote environmentally sustainable and healthy food consumption

³ Georgis, D. (2013). *The better story: Queer affects from the Middle East*. Suny Press.

⁴ <https://www.omamaa.fi/in-english/>

⁵ <https://www.hrankoop.com/>

⁶ <https://www.algarveprimeiro.com>

practices. Horta Urbana Solidária de Faro also distributes the production surplus (organic food baskets) to families in need, as recognized by the municipality's Social Action division. In addition, this initiative collaborates with the Social Solidarity Institution, which is responsible for the garden and works with young people and adults with moderate or severe intellectual disabilities.

Relevant Green Deal policy area

These recommendations from ACCTING are linked to the Farm-to-Fork Strategy⁷ and the policy area “*healthy and affordable food*”⁸. Additionally, the various recommendations also touch upon the policy areas “*fresh air, clean water, healthy soil and biodiversity*” (e.g., by reducing the use of pesticides, emissions from transport, combustible waste) “*future-proof skills training for the transition*” (e.g., providing citizens with skills they will need to cultivate food in times of ecological crisis), and inversely to “*more public transport*” by aiming to reduce needs for transportation. Finally, strengthening the production capacity and market access of local food production addresses the policy area “*globally competitive and resilient industry*”.

⁷ https://food.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2020-05/f2f_action-plan_2020_strategy-info_en.pdf

⁸ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal/agriculture-and-green-deal_en

Valuing indigenous and local knowledge in disaster management and nature protection

Contributors: Martin Felix Gajdusek (ZSI), Esin Düzel (SU), Burcu Borhan Türeli (SU), Carina Green (ORU), Carolin Zorell (ORU), Ayşe Gül Altınay (SU), Gábor Szüdi (ZSI)

Summary

The climate crisis requires the participation of all parts of society and all knowledge resources. There is an urgent need to improve disaster prevention and preparation mechanisms, and to mitigate the impact of the disasters. Less visible but not less impactful, the biodiversity crisis has also reached critical levels, and it is high time to activate and strengthen the resilience potential of society. Indigenous and local knowledge are essential sources in this process. Until now, the main agents that have produced knowledge and policy guidance for the climate and biodiversity crisis have been intergovernmental bodies and the corresponding national groups; this set of recommendations argues for a meaningful, systematic, and non-extractive inclusion of the indigenous and local knowledge (ILK) into the structures of knowledge production and their application. ILK can contribute to both activating disaster management capacities and sustaining functional ecosystems of nature by employing adequate action. The recommendations emphasize the importance of ILK in the design of both local and national policies. For a place-based and regional response, ILK can be of particular importance to the implementation of the policies in the hands of local authorities.

Introduction

top-down, centralized policy

Indigenous and local knowledge (ILK) has received increased attention in the past decades regarding disasters, adaptation to climate-related events, ecological conservation, biodiversity restoration, and many other areas. A centralized nature protection approach or disaster (mitigation) strategy tends to rely on technical solutions, often without considering the experiences and practices of the people who inhabit and use the affected areas of nature. Indigenous and local communities have a thorough, hands-on understanding of their living environment through their daily practices and the inherited intergenerational knowledge. They have knowledge of the historical patterns of natural disasters, observations on the limits of use of

surrounding ecosystems, and a right to live in sustainable environments. This can make them staunch defenders of nature, as well as crucial actors and partners in disaster response. Recently a number of relevant organisations have acknowledged the role of IKL. In its most recent report (Birkmann et al., 2022), the UN Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) recognizes *“the increasing need to consider indigenous knowledge and indigenous people to support integrated strategies in adaptation and mitigation”* to respond adequately to the climate crisis.

Similarly, the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) makes references to indigenous and local knowledge (McElwee et al., 2020)⁹. As well the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) acknowledges the indigenous people’s *“conservation activities on the ground”* (IUCN, 2022) and its *Red List Committee* emphasises the importance of ILK. Referring to our second topic of the recommendations, similarly the United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR) has established the Sendai Framework¹⁰ addressing disaster risk reduction (DRD). This framework identifies as item 11 the importance of *“using traditional and indigenous knowledges for DRD”* (Sterling et al., 2017). However, a wide follow up of the global recognition in practice on local level is often pending. To activate the local potential for place-based biodiversity-positive action, the integration of ILK is a promising starting point. The same applies to improving disaster management. Structural deficits of a top-down disaster management practice are well documented (Panda et al., 2023). Existing structures often neglect the expertise and knowledge held by indigenous and local communities who have an extensive hands-on understanding of their ecosystems and the historical patterns

⁹ <https://www.ipbes.net/indigenous-local-knowledge>

¹⁰ <https://www.undrr.org/publication/monitoring-implementation-sendai-framework-disaster-risk-reduction-2015-2030-snapshot>

of natural disasters. This disconnect hinders the effectiveness of disaster management plans and constrains the full utilization of the valuable insights and practices of indigenous and local communities.

Our research in ACCTING has shown that it is crucial to rethink current approaches and to establish a better dialogue and wilful collaboration between indigenous and local communities and relevant agencies such as the local disaster management organizations and authorities or the relevant nature protection agencies. In ACCTING, the role of vulnerable members of society has been explored in narrative interviews to understand their potential and challenges related to (1) disaster and (2) nature, respectively biodiversity. Our interview partners from vulnerable groups have expressed their viewpoints that are seldom shared with decision-making bodies. Working in specific places and learning from personal stories in ACCTING, the recommendations directly reflect the expressed opinions and give these people a voice. To provide more original insights, the reader can find relevant initiatives that correspond to the challenges at the end of this document.

The narratives, i.e., stories unveil inventive approaches to incorporating indigenous and local knowledge into community practices. They serve as an inspiration for responsible actors to promote more effective and compassionate practices, particularly for the most vulnerable members of our society. While we recognize that both global and EU initiative have set commendable standards for integrating ILK and addressing societal vulnerabilities, the ongoing and expanding climate and biodiversity crises necessitate a more systematic and rigorous integration of ILK. It is imperative to emphasize that only through trust-based and purposeful dialogue can we unlock the full potential of ILK and empower all stakeholders to share and apply this invaluable knowledge. This approach also safeguards against repeating colonial and extractive practices. By fostering local co-creation and innovative participation models involving a diversity of societal actors, we can significantly enhance community ownership of initiatives, a more resilient and sustainable disaster preparedness practice, and effective biodiversity crisis response.

Hence, more equal and culturally appropriate strategies for disaster management and biodiversity action must consider power relations vis-a-vis indigenous and local communities.

Recommendations

1. Administrations and civil society actors in rural regions can develop long-term relationships with indigenous and local communities.

Long-term relationships based on mutual trust can be crucial for disaster preparation, response, and mitigation. Similarly, this applies to the biodiversity crisis. Building long-term relationships includes the cooperation with active organisations, and working with

members from different generations, i.e., the youth and the elderly. Reflecting historical injustices of indigenous and local communities can contribute to establishing a long-term relationship.

2. A true collaboration includes resource-sharing and providing appropriate financial means to support initiatives led or guided by indigenous and local communities.

Current financing resources are often insignificant as ILK communities are not considered a special target group. Encouraging administrations in charge of disaster and biodiversity challenges for targeted resource-sharing ensures that groups holding ILK receive the necessary support by, for example, extending selection criteria of funding schemes. Integrating ILK in local projects that receive support from regional, national, or EU level sources creates ownership and has the potential to facilitate durable resilience. A process of collaborative goal setting together with the ILK communities can trigger commitments and sustainable effects.

promoting collaboration

3. ILK can have an immediate and effective contribution to the disaster prevention and mitigation mechanisms

through climate change observation and assessment of future needs.

A local approach where scientists team up with citizens that rarely get a voice can be a game changer. Actively monitoring and understanding the local but also gendered impacts of climate change and the biodiversity crisis can be a starting point for further action. The on-ground understanding can be a trigger for action, e.g., to mitigate risks, improve disaster response, or increase the adaptive capacity of communities in view of the biodiversity crisis.

4. Recognizing and celebrating positive stories and initiatives to inspire replication and highlight the success and impact of local community-led efforts.

By acknowledging and sharing success stories, we inspire and motivate others to engage in similar initiatives, fostering a culture of innovation and resilience.

5. A gender+ sensitive approach to ILK. Indigenous and local groups often relate to specific gender dynamics, also inherited in their engagements addressing the focus fields of this recommendations.

Recognizing the special role of gender dynamics and gender+ inclusivity is an important contribution to sustained action and equal participation. However, traditional role models and gender dynamics often request a critical reflection to activate all knowledge actors.

6. Active partnerships of concerned administrations with indigenous and local communities can facilitate the bidirectional exchange of knowledge.

The capacities of administrations to interact and co-develop with ILK need to be built up, and such efforts need to be recognized positively. Providing access to education, training, and knowledge-sharing to both the communities and the local administrations can facilitate necessary collaboration and unlock respective capabilities. Moreover, it inherits an opportunity to co-evolve and learn from the interaction.

7. The policy delivery by administrations should be matched with fitting monitoring mechanisms to keep track of evidence of successes (and failures) in the process, especially the collaboration with the vulnerable members of society.

In this case, scientists and experts can support with methodological guidance, to keep track of developments and learn from successful, replicable pathways of interaction.

Target groups

These recommendations relate to two specific stakeholder groups that partly overlap. First and related to disaster, we address organisations and experts who relate to prevention, mitigation, preparedness, response actors and those related to recovery. Addressed organisations include those that directly work in the field with inhabitants or indirectly address them through their programmes and projects. Secondly, local stakeholder engagement is an important feature across a wide range of biodiversity conservation and natural resource management activities, be it in the hands of administrations or supported through funded actions. Other actors, such as civil society organizations, are also addressed through these recommendations.

More specific target groups are:

- Policymakers in their role as program owners that prepare strategies and monitor their implementation through dedicated agencies or other more variable types of delivery actors.
- Policy delivery organisations that organize funding programmes and follow or develop criteria to advise selection processes for funding.
- Administrations that directly deliver activities as part of their daily operations, such as regional forest offices, agricultural advisory services, rangers, health and relief organisations, and municipalities, including their civil protection departments.
- Organisations like activist movements, civil society groups, larger NGOs that deliver place-based or regional actions (such as the WWF programmes addressing biodiversity). CSOs can take on recommendations in their programmes and projects.
- Community leaders, representatives of vulnerable groups who want to inspire other actors to put more attention on indigenous and local knowledge.

Findings from ACCTING

The ACCTING research aims to understand how behavioural change occurs from the perspectives of vulnerable groups. The more specific focus is on what hinders and enables individuals to become more resilient vis-a-vis natural disasters and adapting positive change towards environmental sustainability. 40 narratives relating to disaster management were collected in Italy, Portugal, Sweden, and Turkey; whereas another 50 interviews focusing on nature conservation were conducted in Bulgaria, Hungary, Portugal, Romania, and Turkey. The findings illustrate that knowledge can be an enabling condition for behavioral change when it comes to disaster management and biodiversity conservation. However, ILK is seldom acknowledged by authorities and the groups holding such invaluable knowledge are rarely part of disaster management structures, or of nature protection organisations.

Another point emphasized in the interviews is that policy responses and sound policy implementation are crucial for individuals of vulnerable communities to be able to change their behaviors. Administrations were identified by interviewees as core actors that should take active roles and incorporate place-based knowledge for stimulating positive change. However, some narratives described by contrast administrations that did not support positive behavioral change.

Other factors that contribute to behavioral change include the experience of nature and knowledge cultivated from it; knowledge gained from previous disasters; and solidarity and mutual learning networks. Sustainable action in both thematic fields also relates to administrations: interviewees identified administrations as core actors that should take an active role in stimulating positive change. Some narratives indicate an adverse role of administrations that do not support positive behavioral change. The role of official bodies

and the need to incorporate place-based knowledge in their local action has been repeatedly mentioned by our respondents.

The recommendations presented in this document were developed considering these findings and were related to the core results of the analysis. Enablers of change relate to long-term commitments and knowledge but also to the necessary resources to enable positive responses related to resilience (see recommendations 1 and 2). Social appreciation, collaboration and acknowledging vulnerabilities and solidarity at the same time were cumulated in recommendations 3, 4, and 5. A strong, equally empowered and recognized partnership with the administrative actors was communicated in recommendations 6 and 7.

Better stories - some inspirational cases

In ACCTING, we look for inspiring bottom-up initiatives as Better Stories, a concept borrowed from Dina Georgis¹¹ Findings from the narrative research made it clear that social networks and strong communities are important enablers for change in our often place-based research topics. Therefore, the focus of this policy recommendation – to increase the importance of indigenous and local knowledge in governance practices – rests on solid evidence from local actors. Below follow some illustrative examples of initiatives that could serve as guiding examples for policymakers and civil society actors. The initiatives are meant as inspiring cases for alternative – and more inclusive – practices where dialogue and mutual learning can take place and where indigenous and local knowledge can impact disaster preparation and nature management processes.

BULGARIA

NATIONAL ASSOCIATION OF VOLUNTEERS IN THE REPUBLIC OF BULGARIA, NADRB¹² (Bulgaria) NADRB has proven itself as a capable organization for coordination of any volunteer disaster management effort in Bulgaria that has established a working and robust network of national institutions, municipal authorities and formal and informal local volunteer groups that can be swiftly mobilized. It is actively organizing training courses for volunteers in disaster management and recruitment of such groups, predominantly

¹¹ <https://sunypress.edu/Books/T/The-Better-Story2>

¹² <https://disastermanagement-danube.net/organisations/national-association-of-volunteers-in-the-republic-of-bulgaria/>

on the local level. In other countries, similar organizations have been established in the past decades.

IRELAND

COMMUNITIES 4 CLIMATE ACTION, C4CA¹³ (Ireland). C4CA was established in 2019. Since then, successful training courses have been held in Kildare, Cavan and Wexford. Since the course is free and open to anyone, this makes it accessible for a range of citizens, including vulnerable groups who may not otherwise have access to this type of information and support to get involved in climate action in their communities. Participants have spoken about the value offered by the course, which equips citizens with information on a range of topics - water, waste, procurement, energy, transport, land use and food. Participants have been inspired to take both individual and collective action in their communities and empowered with knowledge to hold policy makers accountable.

TURKEY

YOLDA INITIATIVE¹⁴ (Turkey) Yolda works towards increasing knowledge on the current state and scale of mobile pastoralist communities, their contribution to the ecosystems, and assessing their needs to sustain their livelihoods. Its objective is to learn from them about biodiversity and ecosystems to increase adaptation and resilience to the climate crisis. Yolda conducts scientific research to reveal the connections between mobile pastoralism and its contributions to biodiversity; carrying out advocacy work to support mobile pastoralist groups at national, regional, and global levels; and celebrating their achievements. Yolda closely collaborates with the indigenous nomadic group, Sarıkeçililer. This is one of the mobile pastoralist communities in Turkey which has faced severe challenges in sustaining their livelihood in the last century, particularly in the last recent decades. One of them is the increased access restrictions to their traditional grazing sites. Yolda Initiative supports Sarıkeçililer, in claiming their rights to access their traditional lands and resources and to move freely between summering and wintering grounds, etc.

AUSTRIA

ARCHE NOAH¹⁵ (Austria) The association was founded in 1989 on the initiative of gardeners, farmers and journalists who literally wanted to take seeds back into their own hands, also as the basis of nutrition. Since 1900, the diversity of crops has decreased dramatically worldwide - by 75% - due to the industrialization of agriculture. Today, genetic engineering, seed monopolies, climate change and wars endanger this precious heritage. ARCHE NOAH counters this with a positive vision and numerous activities; it preserves and cares for thousands of endangered types of

¹³ <https://www.esdtraining.net/c4ca>

¹⁴ <https://yolda.org.tr/>

¹⁵ <https://www.arche-noah.at/>

vegetables, fruit and cereals. It is successfully working to bring traditional and rare varieties back into the gardens and onto the market - thanks to the support of over 17,000 dedicated members and sponsors. At the intersection of traditional land use, cultural heritage and traditional food, this initiative contributes to an international network with a dedicated focus on traditional knowledge and sustainable agriculture practice.

GERMANY

QUEICHWIESEN¹⁶ (Germany) community of interest under the leadership of the Ottersheim municipality, farmers, (nature) conservationists and representatives of municipalities where meadow irrigation is actively practised as well as further interested individuals have been coming together since 1996. The agricultural cultivation technique of meadow irrigation is based on the sustainable use of natural resource water. To this day, the tradition is kept alive through the commitment of farmers, associations and foundations and passed on in guided tours and interactive exhibitions. The focus is on knowledge about nature

conservation, natural history and biodiversity as well as its practical application. From 2004 to 2008, a Natura2000 project was realised. In the meantime, around 400 ha of meadows along the Queich can be irrigated again. The municipalities (7 in total) and the water and soil association are responsible for the operation and maintenance of the irrigation facilities. Across Europe traditional land use technics are often biodiversity positive and refer to traditional knowledge, in many cases administrative actors contribute actively to similar initiatives.

Relevant Green Deal policy area

- Wildfire Prevention Action Plan¹⁷
- Biodiversity strategy for 2030¹⁸
- Protecting the environment and oceans with the Green Deal¹⁹

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¹⁶ <https://queichwiesen.de/>

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¹⁸ https://environment.ec.europa.eu/strategy/biodiversity-strategy-2030_en

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Recommendations to Businesses/Employers

Inspiration for CSR policies: To contribute to the Green Deal and become more inclusive

Contributors: Alain Denis & Aart Kerremans (Yellow Window), Gabriele Quinti (Knowledge & Innovation)

Summary

The factsheet provides inspiration for those in charge of designing CSR policies in enterprises, based on insights and lessons learned from the ACCTING research project. These potential actions are directed at making the necessary transition that the Green Deal aims to achieve, in an inclusive way to ensure that no-one is left behind. The recommendations below cover different domains of the Green Deal, for which ACCTING has collected evidence.

Introduction

Businesses and employers have significant potential in promoting positive change related to Green Deal policy goals. Through their CSR policies, they can contribute to the various transition processes that aim to further the sustainability of our societies, while also promoting inclusivity by focusing on mitigating inequalities, so that everyone can be a part of (and benefit from) this transition. Large businesses also have the additional advantage that their CSR policies can serve to inspire and initiate multiplier effects within the sector that they are active in, facilitating change among the businesses that are part of their supply chains. As a result, it is crucial that businesses and employers play their part in the green transition, and that they have the necessary knowledge to accomplish this. The following recommendations aim to inform and inspire CSR policies for a more sustainable and socially just society, based on findings from ACCTING's research activities which are briefly described below. The better stories that follow are included to give an idea of the kinds of inspiring societal initiatives that businesses can support through their CSR policies.

Recommendations

1. Clean and efficient energy transition

- Support and invest in energy communities that address energy poverty.
- Create (if absent) an energy community, including the enterprise and any people (and other businesses) living near the enterprise, addressing energy poverty according to the enterprise's territorial context (as far as possible).
- Support micro-enterprises (close to the enterprise or cooperating in any way with the enterprise) in the design and implementation of Energy Efficiency Measures (EEMs) to increase the environmental sustainability of their business. This support could be provided through personalised advice based on their own experience (on measures such as the introduction of solar panels, software systems to reduce energy consumption, better thermal insulation, optimisation of transport and mobility, etc.). It could also be provided through information and capacity-building on policies and procedures, available funds and projects, existing networks to join, etc.

2. Protecting our biodiversity and ecosystems

- Invest in (local) biodiversity and ecosystem preservation, as well as in 'giving-back programmes' that enable staff to volunteer for nature preservation initiatives during their working hours.
- Support local and/or indigenous communities that are working towards the promotion of biodiversity and the protection of the ecosystem by, among other actions, investing in the education and training of people outside these communities with regard to environmentally beneficial practices.
- Proactively promote the assessment of positive/negative effects for biodiversity in business operations and for the immediate surrounding areas, to increase awareness and to initiate beneficial measures.

3. Healthy food system for people and the planet

- Support and invest in local urban farmers and nearby small-scale food producers who have sustainability as a core value.
- Establish connections with local/short-chain sustainable food producers/farmers and purchase food from them (i.e., for catering needs), while encouraging adjacent companies and other businesses in the sector to do the same.

4. Providing efficient, safe and environmentally friendly transport

- Support and invest in local initiatives that promote cycling, walking, and other modes of sustainable mobility, especially among vulnerable communities (i.e., disabled people, older people, etc.).
- Incentivise use of soft modes of transport among employees (i.e., premium/bonus for cycling to work, boosting car-sharing/carpooling).

5. General recommendations

- Incentivise and reward suppliers that address vulnerabilities and promote behavioural change within their own working environment and through their own supply chains.
- Collectively engage with other businesses in initiatives that enable local enterprises and other community actors to pool resources to counter climate change and address vulnerable individuals, i.e., collective green purchase schemes, collective recycling and reuse initiatives, etc.
- Prioritise sustainable procurement practices by choosing suppliers based on their environmental footprint and sustainability practices, as well as by communicating the importance of taking environmental aspects into account to potential suppliers.
- Foster community partnerships with local environmental groups or other businesses to support broader sustainability initiatives.

Findings from ACCTING that reflect the issue

1) Clean and efficient energy transition

- Energy communities organise collective and citizen-driven energy actions that help pave the way for a clean energy transition, while moving citizens to the fore. They contribute to increasing public involvement of citizens and social actors in renewable energy projects. Solidarity is a key principle of the just, clean energy transition embedded within the Europe Green Deal, which specifically recognises an important role for community energy systems. Nevertheless, energy communities that address energy poverty and try to have vulnerable groups among their members (i.e., Solidarity Energy Communities) are the exception.
- Most micro-enterprises do not design/implement EEMs, both because those who manage these enterprises have little awareness of them and – in cases where they do – because they face multiple obstacles (lack of resources and skills, lack of incentives and assistance from third parties, etc.). Moreover, it is not easy to identify and reach these micro-enterprises: as seen during ACCTING's research phase, these micro-entrepreneurs are often 'hidden'.

obstacles for micro-enterprises

2) Protecting our biodiversity and ecosystems

- Education and training are an important way to promote environmentally beneficial practices and, in the process, change people's behaviour. This is especially the case for younger generations who have grown up in a more technologically intensive world, and who might be more amenable to new forms of training that are attention-grabbing and (potentially) low-cost. Biodiversity protection and habitat preservation – as well as adequate knowledge to engage

in these practices – is emphasised by people living near biodiversity hotspots like natural parks and other natural areas.

- The damage caused by private actors and other economic stakeholders to natural habitats and biodiversity may take many forms, ranging from environmental pollution and overexploitation of natural resources to the wider-scale negative impact of industrialisation and consumerism on smaller

communities adhering to traditional ways of life. Economic motivations that lead to these situations are counteracted by the responsibilities towards nature often upheld by active (local/indigenous) citizens.

3) Healthy food system for people and the planet

- Bottom-up initiatives that allow people to cultivate their own (organic) food – i.e., through (urban) community gardens – can play a crucial role in raising awareness about the sustainability of food systems and their importance for human health. Moreover, urban and small-scale farming has transformative potential: they can enable or complement short food supply chains for locals, as well as for businesses searching for sustainable food sourcing options.

4) Providing efficient, safe and environmentally friendly transport

- People face everyday choices of transport modes for commuting to work, going to school, and other travel. For many, particularly those in transport poverty, these choices are about how they use the limited resources that are available to them (i.e., time, money ...). The transition to more sustainable means of transportation can be used as an opportunity to provide ways of reducing these daily struggles for vulnerable groups, i.e., by cycling, walking, and/or using reliable and frequent public transport.
- Cycling communities and wider social movements can enable change by providing cyclists with a sense of belonging and with a joint platform for promoting cycling as an alternative to using the car. Despite infrastructural challenges in many countries, there are still numerous examples in ACCTING's research of a shift to using bicycles. The turn to the bike reflects how cyclists feel empowered by the autonomy and wellbeing that cycling provides, while

simultaneously being able to save money and contribute to a better environment and climate.

promoting sustainable mobility

Better stories - some inspirational cases

In ACCTING we use '*better stories*', a concept borrowed from Dina Georgis²⁰ to refer to promising practices that identify how a given societal situation can be ameliorated to improve existing practices.

1) Clean and efficient energy transition

ITALY

Energy and Solidarity Community Naples East²¹ (San Giovanni a Teduccio – Italy) is a renewable energy community that is also an educational community. It consists of the Family of Mary Foundation and 40 families in disadvantaged conditions, living in apartments adjacent to the Foundation's headquarters and connected to the same electrical substation. It is a renewable energy initiative that aims to contribute to the energy transition (including through education and awareness-raising), while at the same time fighting energy poverty. These families are in absolute or near-absolute poverty and very often previously lived in conditions of "energy illegality".

DENMARK

Måbjerg BioEnergy²² is a project situated in Måbjerg, an area on the outskirts of Holstebro town in Western Denmark – one of Denmark's most important agricultural areas. The project was a solution to environmental concerns arising from the agricultural sector. While this is an important part of the local economy, concerns arose about the effects of run-off from local animal production. The resultant manure is typically spread onto fields in the area, but this was found to release

²⁰ [Georgis, D. \(2013\). *The better story: Queer affects from the Middle East*. Suny Press.](#)

²¹ <https://www.fondazioneconilsud.it/progetto-sostenuto/comunita-energetica-e-solidale-di-napoli-est/>

²² https://backend.orbit.dtu.dk/ws/portalfiles/portal/9739365/Maabjerg_BioEnergy.pdf

worrying amounts of nitrogen – which was seeping into the fields in question – with negative environmental impacts in the form of water eutrophication in local wetlands. With these wetlands being newly designated as habitat areas by the EU, the local agricultural industry was forced to change its practices. In response to this, a group of local animal farmers (an example of vulnerable workers in carbon-intensive industries, who have been faced with new environmental regulations), working with larger institutional stakeholders to initiate the development of a biogas plant. This allows the manure in question to be converted into biogases (primarily methane), which is used for the production of heat and electricity. The by-products from this process are also harvested and used as fertiliser and as fuel for further energy production.

2) Protecting our biodiversity and ecosystems

SLOVAKIA

The civic association kRaj²³ in Slovakia seeks to change attitudes towards beekeeping, shifting it from a leisure activity and hobby to an activity that protects the sustainability of the landscape and biodiversity, as well as offering a source of secondary income in economically underdeveloped regions. It involves people from local marginalised Roma communities in its activities, as they generally have little prior knowledge of biodiversity issues. The initiative also organises beekeeping and bee product processing courses for people with mental disabilities.

TURKEY

The Women in Fisheries Society²⁴ is a women-led NGO in Turkey that works to improve fisherwomen's conditions, protect coastal ecosystems, and create sustainable economic activities among fishing communities. They organise trainings to empower women fishers, conduct awareness-raising activities, run social change projects developed and led by the women themselves, and carry out research to produce fair solutions that respect both nature and people in the fisheries sector. In their "Blue Planet, Blue Jobs" project, for instance, they established methods to process large amounts of discarded fish.

3) Healthy food system for people and the planet

²³ <https://kraj.sk/>

²⁴ <https://kadinbalikcilardernegi.org/about-us/>

HUNGARY

Kiút²⁵ is a work-integrated training programme based in north-eastern Hungary in which vulnerable people are provided with training and mentoring on how to grow cucumbers on their land and generate income by selling the surplus through companies contracted by the NGO that runs the programme. The target group encompasses people living in extreme poverty – predominantly of Roma origin – who can become registered as primary producers or family entrepreneurs, and thus be able to

live from their jobs as producers of sustainable agricultural food. In addition to practical agricultural, entrepreneurial, and accounting skills, underserved, vulnerable people acquire pro-environmental values and obtain education about sustainable food production and consumption.

DENMARK

Eat Grim²⁶ is a Danish initiative that sells ‘ugly’ fruit and vegetables – which would otherwise be thrown away – at affordable prices. The initiative connects with food suppliers to buy their ‘ugly’ food, which it sells weekly to its community (customers and main supporters) as food boxes. Eat Grim is supported directly by farmers in Denmark and Europe and it is completely led by women farmers. Their main objectives are to reduce food waste and change attitudes around food values by,

for instance, learning to appreciate ‘bad-looking’ food. Moreover, they have a very clear mission related to reducing the broader impact of food production and consumption on the climate.

4) Providing efficient, safe and environmentally friendly transport

IRELAND

The Bike Hub²⁷ is an Irish social enterprise running community bike shops in Dun Laoghaire (a suburb of Dublin) and Dublin City, in partnership with several partners. It aims to make cycling accessible to as many people as possible in the local communities, fostering social and business activities by engaging with the local community through bike-related projects. Targeting young people, older people, women, people with disabilities, and refugees, they offer a range of services,

like organising educational workshops, providing free rentals on a fleet of accessible bikes, restoring previously used bikes and donating them to people with low incomes, and organising bike repair and maintenance training courses.

²⁵ <https://kiutprogram.hu/english/>

²⁶ <https://eatgrim.com/>

²⁷ <https://www.thebikehub.ie/>

ITALY

Job Real Time Carpooling²⁸ is an Italian application designed to facilitate the daily commute of workers through tailored carpooling for individual companies or areas outside urban centres. The app offers a reliable and safe mobility alternative for employees of a business, with the aim of reducing environmental and economic impact by spreading the culture of sustainable mobility. Jojob also organises incentive campaigns for employees to use carpooling, through cashback and gift cards. Moreover, the service allows companies and territories to visualise in real time the results in terms of CO₂, cost and usage savings.

Relevant Green Deal policy areas

- A clean and efficient energy transition²⁹
- Protecting our biodiversity and ecosystems³⁰
- A healthy food system for people and the planet³¹
- Providing efficient, safe and environmentally friendly transport³²

²⁸ <https://www.jojobrt.com/>

²⁹ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal/energy-and-green-deal_en

³⁰ https://environment.ec.europa.eu/strategy/biodiversity-strategy-2030_en

³¹ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal/agriculture-and-green-deal_en

³² https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal/transport-and-green-deal_en

Empower your employees to help mitigate Climate Change: A business-employees alliance promoting behavioural change towards achieving Green Deal goals

Contributors: Nikos Zaharis & Manos Klados (SEERC), Alain Denis (Yellow Window), Giuseppe Pellegrini Masini (NTNU)

Summary

Recognising the important role that companies can play towards fighting Climate Change and based on the preliminary findings of the ACCTING project, we provide a framework for companies to promote inclusiveness and Green Deal policies within their own workforce. The recommendations span aspects including knowledge creation, incentives, and encouragement of collective initiatives. They are addressed to companies of all sizes, as well as organisations that collectively represent companies at the local or sectoral level. The goal is to empower employees to become agents of change within the company and their communities, recognising and addressing issues that link Climate Change with pre-existing, amplified or newly created vulnerabilities and inequalities.

Introduction

Businesses (including SMEs) have a double role to play in the fight against Climate Change:

- To ensure that any negative impact of their activity is addressed and rectified (including but not limited to carbon emissions, waste, and resource depletion).
- To become facilitators of change by enabling and inspiring their employees, supply chains and local communities.

Within the GD a special emphasis is given to “Mobilising Industry for a Clean and Circular Economy”, while business activities also remain relevant to the various thematic GD policies areas (mobility, energy, etc.). In parallel, Climate Change responses and an emphasis on inclusivity can present entrepreneurial opportunities generated by changes in production, in anticipation of changes in the competitive environment. Corporate leaders who recognise these opportunities can have a positive impact both within their company (reputation, morale boosting, employee trust and commitment) and in the environment in which they operate. They can lead by example and promote sustainable behaviour through training, incentives, and initiatives. Suggestions regarding how to do this are given in the following paragraphs.

Findings from ACCTING

Many entrepreneurs have suffered from the crises of recent years, but the explosion of energy costs in late 2021 was more effective in inducing behavioural change. During ACCTING’s first research phase, we found that several measures and technologies have been adopted by entrepreneurs or are being considered by them, such as installing solar panels, renovating their places of business, utilising heat pumps or sun boilers, and changing the software system to reduce energy consumption. In contrast, other identified initiatives have met resistance from entrepreneurs due to higher costs. These include intensifying the use of eco-sustainable products, improving water distribution infrastructure, avoiding the use of chemical materials, producing and retailing sustainable products, and promoting sustainable mobility. Furthermore, our research found that:

- There is a lack of a strong, widely accepted environmental culture among corporations, SMEs and the other involved actors, such as a lack of widespread awareness of the relevance of EEMs, and low prioritisation of environmental incentives.
- SMEs are, generally, not well equipped for the effective practice of environmental measures, due to a lack of expertise.
- There is a low level of trust between energy auditors and businesses, which are reluctant to undertake EEMs and EAs because of the possible economic and operational burden.

- Regulations favouring environmental practices are very complex, because measures are often difficult to access, and the different types of public actors involved need to be coordinated.

Target groups

Our recommendations consider findings from the first cycle of research and co-creation of the ACCTING project. They target three types of organisations:

Large companies or corporations: These usually have the capacity and infrastructure to put together and implement interventions within their workforce to facilitate knowledge creation and sustainable behavioural change, thus enabling achievement of GD targets in an inclusive way. The larger number of employees allows them to more easily facilitate schemes that target specific aspects of the GD (i.e., energy, mobility, food) but that also provide the opportunity to address larger numbers of vulnerable individuals within their workforce. Additionally, engaged and committed corporations may play an important role in inspiring and incentivising their partners throughout their supply chains.

Small and Medium enterprises (micro-enterprises): Their small size means that single SMEs may find some initiatives difficult to implement. Some of them may also lack specific knowledge required. Yet their relatively small size means they can sometimes also implement changes cheaper and more easily. An integrated approach and joint initiatives based on geographical location, industry sector or supply chains are important for these types of companies.

Business associations and other business representing entities (i.e., chambers, clusters etc.): These are established organisations that have a mandate to facilitate cooperation and promote the interest of their members. They may be based on geographical location or on specific industrial sectors or other common interests of several companies.

General recommendations

1. Develop a comprehensive Climate Change (CC) education program for all employees aimed at:

a) Educating them on the threat of CC and the on the danger of increasing vulnerabilities due to the effects of CC

b) Engaging in a creative dialogue on how we can collectively devise responses to CC

c) Encouraging behavioural change at the individual and collective level.

Depending on the local and corporate circumstances this education program can focus on a mix of the following areas:

- Health and inclusiveness, including healthy food that minimises environmental impact.
- Green mobility
- Energy conservation at the office/ production floor and in the home
- Natural disaster response
- Biodiversity
- Inclusion

comprehensive climate change program

2. Encourage and incentivise innovation and engagement by rewarding ideas that conserve energy, facilitate recycling, actively replace unhealthy food, promote the use of green transportation means and, in general, help the company to achieve ambitious environmental and social goals.

Doing so in line with a well-thought ESG strategy that is ideally co-created with the active participation of the employees and local communities. Ensure that the ESG strategy puts a special emphasis on identifying vulnerabilities (existing and potential ones) and includes means to address them within the working environment. Ideally, ESG should be discussed in the company at all levels and include input from civil society and local communities. As part of ESG, an “Inclusivity Action Plan” may be developed.

3. Implement GD measures within the working environment.

Examples of measures:

- Serving local and organic food and avoiding plastic in the internal cafeteria/canteen.
- Creating carpooling plans, coordinated and facilitated by the company’s HR.
- Promoting cycling and the use of public transportation (incentive schemes; cooperation with local authorities in co-defining multimodal transportation that encourages green mobility. I.e., train to bicycle).
- Encouraging energy saving during heating and cooling periods.
- Encouraging and facilitating employee participation in energy communities
- Recycling at every level of activity within the company.

4. Target work-life balance measures, considering the new challenges that CC creates.

Include work-life balance provision to a detailed Corporate Diversity and Inclusion strategy and action plan (part of ESG) that reflects GD and SDGs (especially SDGs 3 {Good health and Wellbeing}, 5 {Gender Equality} and 10 {Reduced Inequalities}).

5. Initiate a cooperation scheme with SMEs in your locality.

This needs to be done by collectively providing training and education to employees regarding climate change and the Green Deal; such that the SMEs can become agents of change within the SMEs community.

Recommendations

These recommendations are directed towards business associations and other business representing entities (i.e., chambers, clusters etc.)

6. Promote best practices with your members, allowing for exchange of knowledge and experiences.

This can be facilitated by:

- Including special sections in annual conferences and other gatherings devoted to behavioural change for fighting CC.
- Developing sector-specific guidelines targeting inclusivity measures, work-life balance promotion, and circular economy practices.
- Organising Local Sustainability Events: Organise or sponsor local events focused on sustainability, such as fairs, workshops, or community clean-up days, to raise awareness and engage the local community.
- Promoting Local and Sustainable Products: Support the local economy and sustainable practices by promoting local and sustainable products among members.
- Organising regular training opportunities for the employees and executives of members.

- Creating rewards celebrating innovation and best practices within members, that target inclusion and green practices.

sharing knowledge & best practices

7. Actively anticipate regulations and advocate for combatting inequalities in the fight against Climate Change at the local, regional and national level.

Business associations needs be prepared beforehand for the climate change induced inequalities an advocate to fight against these inequalities at the local, regional and national level.

8. Engage in social dialogue with trade unions, civil society organisations, and local communities.

creating alliances for change

Businesses should engage in a social dialogue with the trade unions, civil society organizations and local communities with an aim of creating “alliances for change” and regulatory transformations, driven by employees and facilitated/ incentivised by employers.

8. Promote research and innovation activities that tackle Climate Change.

Promotion of research and innovation within the working environment within members in cooperation, with academia and also with civil society organizations. Promote climate related research and innovation agendas to local/ national Research Funding Organisations and with local planning initiatives like the Smart Specialization Strategy.³³

promote research & innovation

9. Assist in Sustainable Funding Opportunities.

Helping the business associations and other business entity members to identify and apply for grants or loans aimed at promoting sustainable business practices such that they can continue their fight against the climate issues.

³³ <https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/what-we-do>

Better stories - some inspirational cases

In ACCTING we use '*better stories*', a concept borrowed from Dina Georgis³⁴, to refer to promising practices that identify how a given societal situation can be ameliorated to improve existing practices.

GREECE

A Greek hotel received an Eco-label accreditation³⁵ thanks to an EU programme. The hotel increased energy efficiency through better thermal isolation, thus significantly decreasing energy consumption, and adopted other relevant measures.

ITALY

An Italian entrepreneur is the owner of a woman-led micro-enterprise which faced serious economic hardships (because of COVID-19 and subsequent crises). Nevertheless, she implemented several ongoing changes to mitigate the enterprise's environmental impact, like recycling of metal and other materials and handling of non-hazardous waste.

NORWAY

Norwegian company³⁶ is searching for environmental and ethical sustainability in the fashion field. This is done by focusing on the recuperation of waste materials from other industrial chains, avoiding the use of chemical materials, checking working conditions along the production chain, and recovering traditions from the past, despite the enormous costs of such innovations.

BELGIUM

A network of small companies in the social economy of Flanders³⁷ carries out energy scans and energy-conserving measures like insulation of walls/roofs, preferably in the homes of socially and financially vulnerable people. Because the companies are part of the social economy, they employ people who typically encounter problems or don't receive many opportunities in the labour market. I.e., 'low-skilled' workers, people with a disability, etc. Once someone is hired, they are trained/educated to carry out the above-mentioned jobs. Socially and financially vulnerable people often, if not always, do not have the resources required for a thorough

³⁴ [Georgis, D. \(2013\). *The better story: Queer affects from the Middle East*. Suny Press.](#)

³⁵ <https://www.villadespinasuites.com/el/>

³⁶ <https://morck.myshopify.com/?fbclid=IwAR2b7IOPjARjkazb3T7d8hy9lchUgcUHLhgAZNKX9W2qyHZQg5Fnz-3Q8Bo>

³⁷ <https://www.saamo.be/west-vlaanderen/westhoek/model/papillon/>

assessment of their homes in terms of energy usage and insulation. The free energy scan and free insulation guidance offered by the network address this problem. Given the recent inflationary pressures on energy prices, their services have become more relevant and urgent for vulnerable people.

Relevant Green Deal policy area

Main GD Policy area:

- Mobilising industry for a green and circular economy³⁸

Other GD policy areas addressed:

- Supplying clean, affordable and secure energy³⁹
- Sustainable and smart mobility strategy⁴⁰
- Farm to fork strategy⁴¹

³⁸ <https://knowww.eu/nodes/5df20a4393cc5125f5416682>

³⁹ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal/repowereu-affordable-secure-and-sustainable-energy-europe_en

⁴⁰ https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/12438-Sustainable-and-Smart-MobilityStrategy_en

⁴¹ https://food.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2020-05/f2f_action-plan_2020_strategy-info_en.pdf

Recommendations to Civil Society Organisations

Inclusive civil society for an inclusive Green Deal

Contributors: Sofia Strid (UGOT), Ana B. Vivas (SEERC), Esin Düzel (SU), Marina Cacace (K&I), Ayşe Gül Altınay (SU), and Burcu Borhan Türeli (SU)

Towards a civil society with greater social impact, in solidarity with vulnerable groups

Non-governmental organisations play a key role in the formation and implementation of European Green Deal policies. They hold expertise in climate change, environmental issues, social justice and sustainable development issues. They work on the ground, locally and in solidarity with local communities, with and for vulnerable groups, representing their voices and interests. In doing so, they enjoy more public trust than governments, corporations, and the media. Non-governmental organisations' participation in climate change negotiations is significant: they provide policymakers and decision-makers with expertise, and they provide legitimacy to environmental governance. However, not all non-governmental organisations have successfully embedded democratic legitimacy in their organisation and actions, diversity in their governance structures and issues, and accountability of the organisation. For the Green Deal to be just and inclusive, it is crucial for civil society organisations to be inclusive, fully reflecting the diversity of the population and stakeholders.

Findings from ACCTING⁴²

Based on an in-depth analysis of 700 bottom-up initiatives the ACCTING consortium concludes that in terms of inclusiveness **these initiatives focus mostly on vulnerable groups based on income, rural/urban gaps, age and ethnicity, while a relatively low number explicitly addressed race and gender+ inequality issues.**

Only a quarter of the initiatives went into processes of decision-making together with local authorities and generated bilateral consensus building. Less than half worked within a framework of multilateral identification of responsibilities, sharing leadership and accountability with other social actors in the field. The analysis of 410 narratives reveals that a sense of 'community belonging' is key enabler for change towards more environmentally friendly behaviour change. Civil society organisations play a key role in this

⁴² Zorell, C., & Strid, S. (eds.) (2023). D3.2 ACCTING Report on first cycle experimental studies. Confidential report delivered to the European Commission 28 April 2023. 281 pages.

community building. Our research shows the great potential for civil society and other public actors to contribute more pro-actively to behaviour change by providing easily accessible information on why and how to do so, but also by promoting new social norms that are aligned with the Green Deal ambitions. In our analyses important and innovating drivers for civil society organisations to reach these ambitions are:

- A focus on **vulnerability and intersectionality**, for example by providing information on sustainable food choices related to identity and creating a sense of belonging to communities, adopting feminist and LGBTQ+ values, linking the fight of eco-change to social change and human rights. Some participants in the ACCTING research mentioned that sustainable food choices values are intertwined with fighting for social rights and change.

A vegan feminist LGBTQI+ activist who sees veganism not as a personal choice but as a political issue says: *“In the past, my relationship with food was about filling my stomach and getting by another day. I was already living through poverty, living through multiple vulnerabilities. Then, all that I experienced, all the encounters I had – working in a yoga studio, getting involved with food collectives, encountering friends from animal-rights struggles, my conversations with them about veganism – led me to a path that was vegan, vegetarian, sensitive to the environment. Of course, all of this has to do with the climate crisis, with industrial food production.”*

- Recognition of the importance of **vulnerable voices to be heard** in order to create an inclusive and just civil society and **to generate just policy alternatives**.

The narrative of a Romanian man with a disability provides a better story of inclusion. He tells the story of creating employment for people with disabilities and sustainable products: *“We produce bags from natural (and some from recycled) cotton and from cloth, as well as backpacks, purses, and some pieces of clothing. We pay a lot of attention to limiting waste. (...) The second important dimension of my work is offering jobs and thus social inclusion for people with disabilities since unemployment in this group is enormous, and many do not get the chance to have proper jobs.”*

- The engagement in **social relationships and the creation of a sense of community and collectiveness** in order to support and achieve behavioural change. An Italian volunteer in various services/associations for the blind, underlines the strength of what can be achieved collectively, in contrast to individually: *“The heritage and experience of people with disabilities should teach to believe in one’s own possibilities and rely on oneself without being afraid to ask for help if some things cannot be done alone.”; “Individually, we do not perceive the change that is possible as a community.”*
- An understanding that the **integration of diversity, inclusion and togetherness lead to wiser and better decisions and solutions, increase the legitimacy and accountability** of organisations, **make inequalities more visible, challenge normativity**. A 40-year-old woman from Greece, illustrates how an inclusive sustainable business strives for both environmental and social aims: *“... together with another four friends, whom I met by chance in my previous work, and with whom*

I shared a common ideology, we founded a small business cooperative with a clear community and social purpose. The coffee place is in a neighbourhood of Thessaloniki city centre, and at the core of our philosophy is to keep the prices of our products as low as we can so that it is accessible to everybody. I am not interested in making as much profit as I can, but I am interested in supporting the community, so I just need to have enough money for living and to make the business sustainable. I feel part of a team/group that has a bigger social purpose.” Their philosophy about accessibility represents a very good example of a vision for businesses which is inclusive of disadvantaged social groups.

- The creation of **solidarity-based communities**.

A Roma flower-seller woman recounted receiving support and care from different actors in her community: *“We have no income, no insurance, nothing, apart from selling flowers daily. (...) The children would beg us to get them something to eat, but what could we do, we had nothing. Thank God, we had good neighbours and friends who gave us some food and supported us. I also received some support from my family who would sometimes send soup and other food they cooked at home. We also got some food support from the municipality. Sometimes the bakeries would give out free bread. That is how we survived through the pandemic. We were half full, half hungry. It was very difficult, really very difficult. After we were allowed to go out and open our flower stand, things got much better.”*

Recommendations

These eight recommendations below are directed towards civil society organisations and non-government organizations.

Transparency, inclusiveness, and equity must guide civil society organisations and responses at all stages. In achieving this, the organisations should promote and support decentralised community decision-making, co-ownership, accessibility, systems of co-existence and kindness.

- 1. Make agendas inclusive so that inequalities become more visible, and the organisation can generate egalitarian/just/inclusive policy alternatives.**
- 2. (Re)design leadership, membership and representation structures with inclusiveness and diversity in mind, leading to more critical approaches to forms of power and normativity, and to wiser decisions, and solutions.**

- 3. Target activities towards more inclusivity and diversity so that nobody is left behind, especially not the most vulnerable communities and those more dramatically impacted by climate change. Organisations are encouraged to adopt the principle "nothing about them, without them" in all their activities and actions.**

- 4. Look for diversified expertise in the organisation, governance, and representation so that actions address social sustainability in addition to environmental and economic sustainability. This can facilitate holistic and integrative approaches that address all dimensions of sustainability.**

- 5. Establish solidarity networks and support the existing formal and informal ones. Solidarity with less-resourced civil society actors and organisations is built to increase the overall capacity of the civil society ecosystems.**

- 6. Collaborate with local communities, particularly with vulnerable or less resourced communities and social actors through empowerment, mentorship, and other supportive mechanisms, to strengthen their activism and advocacy.**

- 7. Facilitate participatory processes and make the bridge with private and other relevant sectors, such as donor organisations, to offer disadvantaged and vulnerable communities a platform to voice their needs and expectations.**

- 8. Enhance the engagement with the private sector to promote awareness and support capacity building on issues relating to discrimination and inequalities in the workplace, which have become more important in the context of climate change. This may be achieved through sharing expertise (providing actual data and training) in the field of climate change and human**

rights, and encouragement and promotion of policies that are eco-friendly and uphold protection of the environment and ensure the rights and well-being of employees.

Better stories - some inspirational cases

In ACCTING, we look for inspiring bottom-up initiatives as *Better Stories* a term borrowed from Dina Georgis⁴³ that refers to promising practices that can instil ideas for how to advance individual and collective behavioural change as envisioned by the Green Deal.

ITALY

THE SOLIDARITY AND ENERGY COMMUNITIES IN FONDO SACCA⁴⁴ (Italy).

The community was created in an area where once a slum stood. The aim of the community was to fight energy poverty. In its place, today, there are buildings equipped with innovative solutions for the production and management of energy from renewable sources. They include socio-educational centres for vulnerable young children and their families, while the energy community also strives for the social integration of former inmates and persons with mental disabilities, who are hosted in some of the residential units.

PORTUGAL

AMADORA⁴⁵ (Portugal).

This initiative is aimed at rescuing and enhancing the social role of senior citizens, their knowledge, and life experiences, through actions that bring senior citizens closer to more concrete forms of active participation, particularly in accident and disaster prevention and protection.

HUNGARY

BAYAERDO⁴⁶ (“Forest of the Witches”, Hungary).

This is an inspiring case of building gender+ solidarities that simultaneously address gender and ethnic exclusion, as well as poverty and unemployment. This organisation consists of a network of volunteers assisting Roma women in a rural village in selling their local produce (mostly mushrooms and berries) with a zero-waste policy in packaging and distribution. Through cooperation, Roma women take pioneer roles in strengthening

⁴³ [Georgis, D. \(2013\). *The better story: Queer affects from the Middle East*. Suny Press](#)

⁴⁴ <https://nesoi.eu/content/fecos-fair-energy-communities>

⁴⁵ <https://www.cm-amadora.pt/pt/>

⁴⁶ <https://www.banyaerdo.hu/>

their deprived societies, increasing their access to healthy and sustainable food, and developing sustainable business skills.

Relevant Green Deal policy area

A healthy food system for people and planet⁴⁷

⁴⁷ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal/agriculture-and-green-deal_en

Local is beautiful

Contributors: Ayşe Gül Altınay (SU), Burcu Borhan Türeli (SU), Marina Cacace (K&I), Ana B. Vivas (SEERC), Sofia Strid (UGOT), Esin Düzel (SU)

Gender+ inclusive agricultural policies and civil society practices for and with small farmers

Agriculture and rural areas are central to the European Green Deal. With the growing food crisis, environmentally sustainable and gender+ inclusive small-scale farming has the potential to play a prominent role in food security, as well as in soil regeneration, reduction of land degradation, mitigation of disasters, and the preservation of biodiversity and cultural diversity. The majority of the 10 million farms in the EU are small farms, only 30% of which are managed by women. There is an increasing amount of literature establishing a link between gender and sustainability, especially regarding sustainable farming practices: women farmers are more often involved in alternative and environmentally friendly approaches.

Yet, existing EU policies fall short of supporting environmentally sustainable, gender inclusive small farming, thereby strengthening existing vulnerabilities and missing opportunities to reach Green Deal objectives. Scientific literature indicates that to move future EU Common Agricultural Policy and other climate and rural policies towards a socially transformative, gender and ecologically-just direction, the push for gender equality will need to come from progressive farmers and civil society.

Findings and from insights from ACCTING⁴⁸

Many governments do not have a coherent and systematic agriculture policy to improve domestic food security and nutrition. This creates significant insecurity and vulnerability among small farmers. Besides, high agricultural costs and economic and production uncertainty serve as major hindrances for change. Some interviews show that small farmers are in debilitating situations, suffer from lack of public (and social) support and are being

⁴⁸ Zorell, C., & Strid, S. (eds.) (2023). D3.2 ACCTING Report on first cycle experimental studies. Confidential report delivered to the European Commission 28 April 2023. 281 pages.

pushed out of agricultural production. To compensate for the lack of public support, results from ACCTING highlights how some small farmers are engaged in cooperation practices, purchasing together and sharing tools and equipment for sustainable farming that they would not be able to afford individually. However, the competition with large agricultural mastodons remains an unequal struggle. Further research by ACCTING implicitly addresses the links between gender (+) equality, food security, and nutrition. We can conclude that women fulfil significant roles and responsibilities to ensure food security and nutrition and to enable behavioural change for themselves, their children, and their families, even in the most limited and challenging conditions.

Below are some of the findings and narratives from ACCTING that reveal how women try to overcome gender inequalities in the food system:

- Growing food in their gardens, farms, or community gardens not only to generate income but also to promote food safety and provide access to food or food products of higher quality.
In a narrative, from an ecofeminist activist involved in the environmental struggles in Aegean Turkey, there is a reflection about the lack of support for small farmers in Turkey: *“The transition to corporate farming in our region worries me a lot. Much of the support offered today is inefficient at transferring income to small-scale farmers because the government supports corporate agriculture and industrial farming. Companies have been merging small plots of land to form large apple orchards, which is also worrying.”* Her narrative also reveals the relationship between unsustainable agriculture, food insecurity, and wildlife: *“Whereas the garden used to be full of colourful wildflowers, now we see fewer species such as St. John's wort. It has also become more challenging to encounter wildlife. We used to see roe deer cubs in our field occasionally. We don't see them much anymore. They probably go deeper into the forests to find food.”*
- Preparing food sources for the entire year, especially winter, by drying, canning, and pickling vegetables. A 30-year-old micro-entrepreneur in the food sector, highlights cooperation to make up for the lack of resources and support for small companies in the sector.
“We are four. All young people. Our farm produces galettes, corn chips, and various kinds of flour, crisps and biscuits. (...) We believe much more in cooperation than in competition. For example, we make our maize galettes production equipment available for all the farms in the area that cannot afford to buy a production plant for their small production. Only through cooperation can small and micro companies in our sector withstand competition with large multinationals.”
- Undertaking responsible waste-management.
- Relying on intimate relations and social networks, receiving support from their mothers or grandmothers in administering the food of the household, but also in the promotion of healthy eating habits within the family and especially among young children.
- Receiving support from their girl children to take care of the housework and cooking while the mothers work in the field (which creates concerns regarding the exploitation of children, especially of girls).
- Leading or partaking in activism to protect their livelihoods (their gardens, forests and the ecological balance of the area) for their survival and self-sustainability.

Recommendations

The recommendations below are intended for the policy makers. New policies are needed at all levels of governance (local, regional, national and EU) to support the gender+ inclusive implementation of the European Green Deal, regarding rural areas in general and small farming in particular. We call on all policy makers to:

- 1. Provide incentives (such as announcing new awards and making existing ones accessible) for environmentally sustainable and gender+ inclusive small farming practices and initiatives such as waste management, composting, and soil regeneration to enable a bottom-up transformation.**
- 2. Design more financially and technologically accessible alternatives to certification systems (including organic certification), such as ‘participatory guarantee systems’ that operate at the local level in order to enable fair access to certification for new farmers, women, and other vulnerable groups.**
- 3. Create gender+ inclusive public spaces through participatory urban planning and design, enabling environmentally sustainable small farms and women’s food cooperatives to sell their produce at the local level.**
- 4. Establish regulations that require public procurement (school canteens, hospitals, public offices, employee canteens, etc.) to prioritise products from local farmers and particularly women, BIPOC (black, indigenous and people of colour) and indigenous-led farms and food-cooperatives. This would help in restoring a fairer competition with industrial producers that are not required to integrate social and environmental costs.**

5. **Support farmers' right to seeds and their capacity to grow food to feed themselves and other people adequately, particularly in line with Article 14 of the Convention of the Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW) on rural women's rights to seeds, as they play a key role in local and global food systems and food security.**
6. **Develop gender+ inclusive mechanisms for networking, knowledge-sharing and collaboration between policymakers, experts, civil society organisations, and small farmers; and reform the current institutional structures (such as farming advisory systems) to have gender+ inclusive participatory governance.**
7. **Create gender+ inclusive education and training programs for small farmers that weave together local, indigenous, gender+ experiences and wisdom with scientific research towards the development of environmentally sustainable, fair, and healthier farming and food systems.**
8. **Promote gender+ inclusive agroecological farming practices that prioritise local supply chains, traditional local knowledge, intergenerational exchange, protecting wildlife habitat and water quality through sustainable agricultural practices free of synthetic pesticides and chemical fertilisers, while paying attention to gender, cultural and racial diversity.**

Recommendations

These recommendations are directed towards the civil society organizations, they are based on our narrative research, and on the mapping of the better stories of those civil society organisations that are making a positive impact in this field. **We call on all civil society organisations, cooperatives (both producer- and consumer-led),**

professional associations (particularly of agricultural and forest engineers) and trade unions to develop closer collaboration and networking with small farmers to:

- 1. Co-create policy and action proposals for environmentally sustainable, fair, and gender+ inclusive local food systems.**
- 2. Raise public awareness about the significance of local, seasonal food consumption for human, animal and planetary health, and co-create tools and processes for more environmentally sustainable, fair, and gender+ inclusive practices in small farming.**
- 3. Support small farmers in reaching consumers without intermediaries, for economic and environmental sustainability, addressing the significance of short supply chains for mitigating the climate crisis.**
- 4. Adopt a gender+ perspective, make the local knowledge and wisdom of small farmers (particularly women, BIPOC, migrant and indigenous) regarding sustainable food systems, biodiversity, soil regeneration and multispecies survival visible and accessible for the public, as well as for policymakers. This could be achieved by archiving and making visible better stories of environmentally sustainable and gender+ inclusive small farming practices and initiatives, and through collaborative publishing, training, outreach, lobbying, and dissemination activities.**
- 5. Create local, regional, national and international networks among (particularly women, BIPOC, migrant, and indigenous) small farmers and farmers' associations and cooperatives engaged in environmentally sustainable farming practices.**

Better stories - some inspirational cases

In ACCTING, we look for inspiring bottom-up initiatives as *Better Stories* borrowed from Dina Georgis⁴⁹ that refer to practices on how to advance individual and collective behavioural change as envisioned by the Green Deal.

Terras de Cascais (Lands of Cascais)⁵⁰ (Portugal)

This is an inspiring case of building gender+ solidarities that simultaneously address gender and ethnic exclusion, as well as poverty and unemployment. This organisation consists of a network of volunteers assisting Roma women in a rural village in selling their local produce (mostly mushrooms and berries) with a zero-waste policy in packaging and distribution. Through cooperation, Roma women take pioneer roles in strengthening their deprived societies, increasing their access to healthy and sustainable food, and developing sustainable business skills.

SISTER LAND FARMS⁵¹ (USA).

This was a queer-owned, worker-run farm cooperative/school that provides food for the food banks, supports farmers (especially queer and indigenous), and partners with tribal youth for their educational activities. What is most inspiring in their practice is that as an organisation run by queer, indigenous, worker groups, they aim to reflect their experiences of marginalisation into farming practices to “elevate the disenfranchised and historically ignored” and to tackle racism, poverty, gender-based discrimination and the climate crisis in a spirit of “collectivism and community.”

MULHER - WOMEN’S MOVEMENT OF THE XINGU INDIGENOUS RESERVATION ASSOCIATION⁵² (BRAZIL).

The campaign carried out by ATIX Mulher during the pandemic in 2020 for food and agricultural tools for the 16 ethnic groups of the indigenous reservation is an example of ensuring women's emancipation and empowerment within traditional structures of indigenous communities in central Brazil.

KADIKÖY COOPERATIVE⁵³ (Turkey)

A consumer cooperative that supports local and regional food production and transforms consumer consumption behaviour and habits in a highly densely populated neighbourhood of Istanbul. Developing trust and caring relationships and knowledge exchange among the

⁴⁹ [Georgis, D. \(2013\). *The better story: Queer affects from the Middle East*. Suny Press.](#)

⁵⁰ <https://ambiente.cascais.pt/pt/terrasdecascais/terras-cascais>

⁵¹ <https://www.sisterlandfarms.com/farm-school>

⁵² <https://www.equatorinitiative.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/ATIX-Case-Study-English-r3.pdf>

⁵³ https://www.facebook.com/KadikoyKoop/?locale=tr_TR

producers, stakeholders, and consumers in an alternative food network that replaces third-party certification with participatory guaranteed systems, this co-op supports small local producers who cannot access conventional markets to sell their organic and pesticide-free products without certification. Urban consumers also access a wide diversity of local products and contribute to the social sustainability of various regional/rural areas and the debate around organic certification.

Other inspiring *better stories* to look at

LA KUMPANIA (ITALY), <https://www.lakumpania.it/>

KILOMBO (Spain), Kilombo. Ecosistemas econòmics i culturals per al bon viure - (lafundicio.net)

Relevant Green Deal policy area

- European Green Deal “Farm to Work Strategy: For a Fair, Healthy and Environmentally Friendly Food System”⁵⁴
- The New CAP (Common Agricultural Policy, (2023-2027))⁵⁵,
- The EU Small Farmers Scheme(2017)⁵⁶
- Action Plan for Organic Production in the EU (2021)⁵⁷

⁵⁴ https://food.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2020-05/f2f_action-plan_2020_strategy-info_en.pdf

⁵⁵ https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/common-agricultural-policy/cap-overview/cap-2023-27_en

⁵⁶ https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2018-10/small-farmers-scheme_en_0.pdf

⁵⁷ https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/farming/organic-farming/organic-action-plan_en

Further development

Following the aim of ACCTING project to address the impact of Green Deal policies on vulnerable groups, prevent inequalities, and produce knowledge and innovations to advance behavioural change at individual and collective levels for an inclusive and equal European Green Deal, a second set of policy recommendations will be developed in the second part of the project. These recommendations will take into account the research results from the second ACCTING research cycle (WP3) including the Open Studios (WP4) as well as the results from the Pilot Actions (WP5). In addition, for the wider promotion and uptake of these recommendations to the target groups, they will be widely advocated through dissemination and outreach activities (WP7). These recommendations will form the future deliverable D5.4.

